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THE IRON PILLAR AT DHĀR.

L YING at Dhār, in Central India, are three portions of a great iron column with a total length of 43 feet 4 inches, and an average width of $10\frac{1}{4}$ " each way. The longest portion measures 24 feet 3 inches, and is square in section throughout; the second 11 feet 7 inches, of which 8 feet 6 inches is square and 3 feet 1 inch of octagonal section; and the third piece, 7 feet 6 inches in length, and, with the exception of a circular collar at the end, about 8 inches deep, is of octagonal section throughout. In February last (1903) the longest piece was lying outside, and at a short distance from the north entrance to the great courtyard of Dilāvar Khān's mosque, known on this account as the Lāt Masjid. The second portion was lying at the Ānand High School, where a museum has lately been established, while the shortest length was set up and fixed in a masonry basement in the public gardens known as the *Lāl Bāgh*, not far from the High School.

The length at Dilāvar Khān's mosque, which has attracted most attention, lies with its lower end tilted upwards and resting against the high masonry basement upon which it was set up by Dilāvar Khān. The proper lower end, now the highest, though square like the rest of its length, is, as in the case of the Delhi iron column, slightly bulbous, being 11 to $11\frac{1}{4}$ " wide at 2 feet from the end, while the rest measures $10\frac{1}{4}$ to $10\frac{1}{2}$ ". At 6 feet from the proper upper end is a short inscription of Akbar's, dated in the 44th year of his reign, recording his halt here on his way to the Dakhan, but which, if the column were re-erected, would be upside down. This is due to the inscription having been engraved while the column was lying in its present position, it being upon the upper side as it lies, and in the easiest position for an engraver to work at it, standing at the side of the pillar with the slant, like a desk, before him. Were the column standing in its last position, the inscription would be over 16 feet above the point where the pillar emerged from the basement, and, as already said, upside down!

Upon other parts of the pillar are names and letters in the Devanāgarī character, all apparently later than the fourteenth century, but which, unlike Akbar's inscription, are engraved with the proper side up. Among these is a group of several names of visitors of the goldsmith caste, each name having "soni" for *sonār* attached to it, the last of which seems to read "Jasu soni" for Yesvant Sonār. There appears also to be a date immediately after the names, but it is very indistinct. These names are

between 6 feet 11 inches and 7 feet 6 inches from the proper lower end of the pillar. Twenty inches of the end was let into the socket in the great boulders when it stood upright on its present site, which would leave the inscription between 5 feet 3 inches and 5 feet 10 inches from the level upon which the engraver might have stood, a fairly easy height for him to work at. When the pillar was entire and unbroken, set up in its original position, probably another foot or more of it was embedded in the basement, and this would make the position of these names, if they then existed, the very best possible for the greatest ease in engraving. There are also several small symbols and a Persian word or two, but they are all rather scratched in than engraved. It will be noticed from the drawing which accompanies this that all these Devanāgarī letters and names are about the same level, and none occur upon the upper parts of the pillar, nor upon the other two fragments, showing clearly that these characters were not engraved after the final fall of the pillar.

Upon the masonry basement stand the three great rock boulders, which were bound together by iron bands and had a socket in the top, 20 inches deep, in which the foot of the pillar was gripped. The iron bands securing these passed round them horizontally, and their pressure was spread over the boulders by vertical flat iron bars inserted at intervals under the bands in slots cut for the purpose. In fact the whole was faggotted around the end of the pillar.

The piece lying at the Ānand High School is, for 8 feet of its length, of the same section as the last, and was, no doubt, a continuation of the Lāt Masjīd length. In this piece the square changes to an octagon, but a very irregular one.

The piece in the Lāl Bāgh, which has lately been taken out of its masonry basement in order to get its measurements correctly, was, without doubt, a further continuation of this second piece. Mr. Lele, the State Superintendent of Education, who made the measurements, doubts this on account of its smaller perimeter measurement, but, I think, he overlooks the fact that, in two figures, a square and an octagon formed off the same square, with the same diameter from side to side, the perimeter measurement of the octagon will be very much less than that of the square. His own perimeter measurement of $34\frac{1}{2}$ " , taken about the middle of the length, works out to a diameter from side to side of fully $10\frac{1}{2}$ ". The upper end of this piece has a round neck, about 8 inches deep, a little smaller in diameter than the rest of the pillar, as if it were intended to hold a collar or fit into a socket of a capital.

One curious thing about all three sections of this great column is the presence of a number of small holes at intervals in its sides, varying in depth from $1\frac{3}{4}$ " to 3 inches, and in diameter about $1\frac{1}{4}$ ". They run up each of the four sides of the square shaft and the corresponding faces of the octagon. In the drawing I have shown the four faces of each of the three lengths of the pillar; but whether, in my arrangement, I have hit off the proper continuation of the faces, one above the other, I cannot say, since I have nothing to guide me. To find out properly which end fits which end, and which faces are the proper continuations of those on the other pieces, it would be necessary to take casts of the joining ends of the different lengths and to fit them together by trial, since the columns themselves are too unwieldy to experiment with and are not even near each other.

THE IRON PILLAR AT DHAR.
DIAGRAM OF ITS FOUR FACES.

FROM THE MUSEUMS
OF BOMBAY

FROM THE MUSEUMS
OF BOMBAY

FROM MR ABU

FROM BHATKAL NEETHI KANARA

IRON PILLAR. DELHI.

FROM ERAN. CENT. INDIA

FROM BALAGANVE. MAIBUR.

1st FACE

2nd FACE

3rd FACE

4th FACE

DUMMALA MAIBURAS PRSBY.

It has been thought that these holes were intended for pegs to carry lights, presuming the column to have been a *dīpadāna* or lamp-post, or to form a ladder for a person to climb to the top to light a fire there. My own opinion is, for reasons I will endeavour to show, that the column was not used as either a *dīpadāna* or beacon, and that no pegs ever occupied the holes for that purpose. Had the holes been intended for any such permanent use, the pegs would have been welded in hot with the rest of the metal, and would not have come out so easily as they seem to have done. One only refused to move, and it has been broken off; there are none in any of the other holes, which, I think, shows they were worked in cold, in order that they should not be permanently welded to the rest of the metal, and were only used for temporary purposes. The holes, in all probability, were made as the mass of the pillar was built up, in order to hold the ends of crowbars or levers with which the workmen could the better handle and roll over the great heavy column as bit by bit of semi-molten metal was added and welded on to the white hot stump of the shaft. The crowbars were removed and shifted from place to place as required; one stuck and was chipped off, leaving the end in the hole.

At the bottom of the length at the Lāt Masjid is a hole about 3 inches deep. This was evidently intended for an iron peg in the basement to fit into, to prevent the column from slipping sideways from its bed when it was set up.

The very meagre details of its history give us no clue as to who caused it to be made, or for what purpose it was forged. I think there was but one purpose to which it could have been put—to carry an image or symbol, set up before a temple, either as a special gift to the temple or as a *jayastambha*, or column of victory. *Jayastambhas* were common enough all over the country, two, at least, of which were of iron, *viz.*, that at Delhi and another of more modest proportions on Mount Ābu. This latter, which stands 12 feet 9 inches high, is set up in the courtyard of the temple of Achalesvara and is surmounted by a Śaiva *triśūla*. I have given a sketch of it upon the accompanying drawing. This pillar is said to have been made out of the arms cast away by the flying Muhammadans when chased down the hill by the bees.¹

The only thing recorded in an inscription² of a certain southern King Tiluṅga-vidya is that he erected a pillar of victory, with a figure of Garuḍa on the top, at Ujayapurī. That the Paramāra kings of Mālvā were no strangers to such erections we learn from the Udaypur *praśasti* of those kings,³ where it is stated that Vairisimha, one of the early kings of that line, composed his own eulogy by erecting pillars of victory; and, curiously enough, this is practically the only thing recorded of him.

The earliest columns or *lāts* that we have are the round Aśoka *lāts*, bearing his edicts, and generally surmounted by one or more lions. Following them are the Gupta columns, generally square below, rising into octagonal, sixteen-sided, and circular section as they ascend, such as the Eraṇ⁴ and Paṭhāri examples. A very interesting pillar, erected for quite a different purpose, is that at Bijayagaḍh, set up as a sacrificial pillar (*yūpa*) by Vishṇuvaradhana in A.D. 371.¹ This pillar, of a single

¹ It is dated Sam. 1468 (A.D. 1412), about the time that general revolts were raised against 'Alā-al-dīn, just before his death.

² *Epig. Ind.*, Vol. VII, p. 121.

³ *Epig. Ind.*, Vol. I, p. 237.

⁴ See drawing, also General Sir A. Cunningham's *Reports*, Vol. VI.

block of red sandstone, rises to a height of 26 feet 3 inches, 3 feet 8 inches of which is square, while the rest is a tapering octagonal shaft broken off at the top. Later on we have frequent references to the setting up of *jayastambhas* or pillars of victory. The Narwār pillar of the Tomara Kings is such a one, supposed to have been erected in the reign of *Shāh Jahān*.² In two copperplate grants, *Bīchāṇa*,³ the governor of the southern provinces under the Yādava king *Sīnghāṇa*, is recorded to have set up a pillar of victory upon the banks of the *Kāverī* about A.D. 1238. Again the Chola King *Rājendradeva* is said, in a copperplate grant, to have erected a *jayastambha* at *Kollāpuram*.⁴

That the pillar was probably surmounted by an image of *Garuḍa* I should think not unlikely from the fact that most of the copperplate grants of this dynasty have a representation of *Garuḍa* engraved upon them by way of a seal.⁵ It was evidently a royal device used by many of those rulers. In this case it would have stood before a *Vaiṣṇava* temple, and that *Vaiṣṇava* worship was prevalent in this State is shown by the numbers of images of *Viṣṇu* already gathered together at the lately established museum at *Dhār*. Or, as at *Ābu*, it might have been surmounted by a *triśūla*. The two great columns in the courtyard of the monolithic temple of *Kailāsa* at *Elurā* were also surmounted by *triśūlas*.⁶ At the village of *Balagāṃve* in *Maisūr*, not far from the southern borders of the Bombay Presidency, stands a tall graceful column surmounted by an image of *Gaṇḍabheruṇḍa*,⁷ which was, as an inscription upon it tells us, set up before a temple of the god *Jagadekamalleśvara*.

In connection with the possibility of the iron column having been surmounted by a *triśūla* a curious idea presents itself. The finial adopted by the *Muhammādans* for the domes of their earliest buildings at *Māṇḍu* is practically a *triśūla* with the central prong removed, or rather dwarfed. On the accompanying drawing I have given sketches of both. Did the Hindu *triśūla*, which for so long had presided over the city of *Māṇḍu*, give them the idea for their finial? Or did they, as they adapted so many Hindu things to their own use, press this idolatrous symbol, in its new guise, into the service of *Allah*?

Stone columns, generally very ornamental in design, were set up in front of *Jaina* temples, especially in the *Kanarese* country, where we still find many examples, such as the one at *Bhatkal* sketched in the drawing. They carried little images within a small canopy upon the top. I have found these with their images in *North Kanara*. *Fergusson* gives illustrations of two, Nos. 149 and 155, and another, No. 188, where the image and canopy have been removed and a five-branched iron brazier placed in their stead. I do not believe this was originally so. Curiously enough we find just such a pillar as the first two, surmounted by a little canopy for an image,

¹ General Sir A. Cunningham's *Reports*, Vol. VI, p. 59, and *Corpus Inscriptionum*, Vol. III, p. 252.

² General Sir A. Cunningham's *Reports*, Vol. II, p. 324.

³ *Journ. Bom. Br. R. A. Soc.*, Vol. XV, p. 383, and Vol. XII, p. 43.

⁴ *Epig. Ind.*, Vol. VII, p. 145.

⁵ See *Mandhata plates*, *Epig. Ind.*, Vol. III, p. 46. *Ujjain plates*, *Ind. Ant.*, Vol. XIX, p. 345; and see also note 87, *Epig. Ind.*, Vol. I, p. 237; and *Ind. Ant.*, Vol. VI, p. 49.

⁶ *Cave Temples of India*, pp. 452-3.

⁷ A fabulous bird which preyed upon elephants, represented sometimes as a man with two birds' heads looking different ways; see drawing.

in the middle of a tank at Nalcha, on the roadside between Dhār and Māṇḍu. It is illustrated in Captain Barnes' account in the *Journal of the Bombay Branch of the Royal Asiatic Society*, No. LVIII, Vol. XXI. This was not a *dīpamālā* or *dīpadāna* as supposed. In the middle of a tank, on a dark night, it would have been a veritable *ignis fatuus*.

All these Jaina columns are of stone, and are comparatively unimportant and non-essential adjuncts to the temples they adorn, and it is hardly likely anyone would have lavished so much money and labour upon so colossal an undertaking in iron, a material they were not in the habit of working up in those days into anything more massive or important than military and agricultural implements. It was, no doubt, made long before the people had learnt to manipulate large masses of metal in making cannon.

Even far less important and essential to a temple is a *dīpadāna*, and the very design of the Dhār column excludes the supposition that it was made for that purpose. Where were the lights to be placed? *Dīpadānas*, as we know them, are generally clumsy conical, or pyramidal towers of masonry covered from top to bottom with innumerable little projections or pigeon-holes, at perfectly regular intervals, to hold lights. In the accompanying drawing I have given a sketch of one from Hatihar,¹ which is much more attenuated and graceful than they are generally found. The *dīpadāna* is for a display of lights after dark. In the case of the iron column there would have been but a poor display with one solitary oil light placed some 50 feet above one's head, and there were certainly no arrangements for lights upon the pillar elsewhere. As a beacon, with a brazier on the top, it will be seen that the holes, if they ever held pegs to climb by, are in some instances too far apart to enable a man, even unencumbered with fuel for the fire, to scale the column. In some places they would, for the same purpose, be unnecessarily close together, while they also start nearer the ground than there would be any occasion for; in fact, some of them would have been actually embedded in the basement with the foot of the column.

We must therefore dismiss at once the idea of a *dīpamālā* as its purpose. It would have been far cheaper and more effective to have had a masonry *dīpamālā* with its scores of ledges for lights. The *dīpamālā* is so very subordinate and non-essential an adjunct to a temple that it seems too much to suppose that such a costly *chef-d'œuvre* of the blacksmith's skill should be degraded to so unworthy a purpose. This was to have been its lot, had Jahāngīr succeeded in carting it to Agra as he wished.

It might be mentioned, in passing, that the Jains have no *dīpamālās* attached to their temples, since the bright lights would lure myriads of tiny lives to sudden death, and even the setting up of columns crowned with images, as already referred to, does not seem to have been practised by the Jains so far north.

What we know of the column, from history, is very little. My idea is that it was originally set up before the principal temple of Māṇḍu,² probably a Vaiṣṇava one, which occupied the site of the present Jāmi' Masjid. We know, and they have

¹ *Chālukyan Arch.*, by A. Rea, Plate CIX.

² Possibly the Muhammadan tower of victory of Maḥmūd I. was raised upon the spot occupied by the iron column.

exultingly recorded the fact, in many of their inscriptions, that the Muhammadans, when they first overran the country, made a practice of destroying the chief temple at most places they visited and building their first Jāmi' Masjid upon its site. The pillar was probably entire when 'Ainu-l-Mulk Multānī was sent to effect the conquest of Mālvā in A.D. 1304. After being thrown down by the Muhammadans, and its shaft broken into *two* pieces, which lay about for a hundred years, the greater length was brought down by Dilāvar Khān Ghori, about A.D. 1405, to be erected before the mosque he had just built at Dhār. Here it remained until Sulṭān Bahādur of Gujarāt, in A.D. 1531, reduced Māṇḍu and wiped out its dynasty. He is said, by Jahāngīr, to have wished to carry the pillar to Gujarāt, and, in attempting to do so, allowed it to fall, when it broke into two pieces of 22 and 13 feet. The longer of these *two* pieces, which is really 24 feet 3 inches in length, is lying where it fell, while the shorter piece seems to have been carried away, and was set up in the garden of the Agency or Guest House at Dhār, where Dr. Führer says he saw it surmounted with a bell-capital¹ in 1893. It was subsequently taken to the newly started museum at the Ānand High School, where it now lies.

This piece must not be confused with the smaller piece, 7 feet 6 inches in length, set up, as already stated, in the Lāl Bāgh. This third piece, that which was broken off when the pillar was first thrown down at Māṇḍu, remained up there until recently, when it was brought down to Dhār. This same piece, Dr. Führer tells us in his Progress Report, was then standing opposite the Jāmi' Masjid at that place. The late Sir James Campbell, in his account of Māṇḍu,² says: "In front of the gateway of the great mosque, in the centre of a masonry plinth about 3 feet high, stands an iron pillar about a foot in diameter at the base and 20 feet high." Upon this same basement, at our visit in February last, we found a tall iron flagstaff, known as Allauddal's *sāng* (spear), wrapped round with an old flag. It is but a few inches in diameter. Perhaps Sir James has, in his notes, substituted the perimeter measure of this for the diameter. Mr. Lele's information on this point is that this piece of the column was brought from the front courtyard of the Hindolā Maḥal at Māṇḍu. In an account of Māṇḍu by a "Bombay Subaltern," published in 1844, it is said, in describing the buildings in front of the Jāmi' Masjid entrance porch, "On the left, in front of the present quarters of some sepoy's of the Dhār Raja, is an iron pole now used as a flagstaff."³ And again, speaking of the Taweli Maḥal it is said that, outside that building, "is a large piece of iron several tons in weight—a remnant of the blacksmith's stock-in-trade, which he forgot to convert into gold."⁴ The first undoubtedly refers to the present iron flagstaff, while the second refers to the small piece of the *lāt* subsequently brought down to Dhār. It is curious how both Sir James Campbell

¹ See his *Progress Report* for the year ending 30th June, 1893, p. 21. In reply to enquiries made through Captain Barnes regarding this bell-capital, Mr. Lele writes: "As soon as your letter came, I drove to the Agency House and made a search for the bell-capital near the Havaladar's house. Nothing like it was found there or anywhere else. But on further enquiries I found, near the *bāghbān's* house, a flat octagonal slab of ordinary blackstone, which old people say rested upon the *lāt* while it was standing in the Agency garden. It formed the seat of a stone figure of Napoleon Bonaparte on horseback by which the *lāt* was surmounted. When Dr. Führer visited Dhār this slab with its support might have looked to him bell-shaped."

² *Four. Bom. Br. R. A. S.*, Vol. XIX, p. 157 (1895).

³ *Hist. of Mandu, the ancient capital of Malwa*, by A Subaltern (a reprint: Bom. Ednl. Socy's Press), p. 13.

⁴ *Id.* p. 16.

and Dr. Führer make the same mistake, unless the one simply copied his account from the other.

Who made the column and where was the iron got from? I take it for granted it is of iron, and from a superficial examination it certainly appears to be so: I am not aware of any analysis of the metal having been made. It is remarkable that the column contains no original record, but it may be that the shaft, as it is, is in an unfinished state, or that the inscription, if any, was upon the basement upon which it was set up. The discovery of the capital, which is quite possible, would, perhaps, give us a clue. I should not be surprised to know that the image which crowned the column, together with the mutilated image of the principal deity of the temple, lies buried ignominiously beneath the floor, or is embedded in the walls of the great mosque, at Māṇḍu. Stone images, so stowed away, are seen peeping out of breaches in the wall of most of the buildings there.

Although we know absolutely nothing of its origin, still there is a certain fascination in hazarding guesses and building up pretty theories which may or may not be true. Presuming it to have been a *jayastambha*, or column of victory, such as the only two other iron pillars we know of were, we might discard the reference to those set up by Vairisimha I., as being too remote and mythical. We can only recall the occasions upon which, as matters of history, these kings claimed to have scored decisive and crushing victories over their enemies, and to imagine any one of these to have been the occasion for its erection. One of the most important of the early victories was that gained by Rājā Bhoja's General Kulachandra over Bhīma Deva I. of Gujarāt. These two kings and their successors were lifelong and natural enemies.

This General took and entered Anhilvāda, sowed cowries at the gate of the palace, and brought away with him a *Ḍaya patra* or official acknowledgment of victory from the enemy.¹ Not long afterwards the Gujarāt king, Siddharāja invaded Mālvā and carried off King Yaśovarmadeva as prisoner. This disgrace was to be wiped out, and Arjunavarmadeva, a later king, did it. We are told that he laid Gujarāt waste. What more natural than that having completely conquered the country, he should disarm it; and what better calculated to commemorate this great victory than this unique iron column, made from the very arms and booty taken from the enemy? No wonder then Bahādur Shāh wished to carry back to Gujarāt that which was its own.

The people believe the column to be made of *pañcarasa* or *aṣṭa dhātu*, an alloy of five or eight metals. Some light silvery looking spots have given rise to this

¹ *Ep. Ind.*, Vol. I, p. 231.

² *Note* :—The measurements of the three sections of the iron pillar, given in the article above, were made by Mr. Lele, the Superintendent of State Education of Dhār, but since the article was written I have personally taken fresh measurements of the two smaller sections, as a doubt was expressed as to their both having been parts of the same pillar. The smallest piece, with the collar or neck at one end, measures 2' 9½" round its octagonal shaft, while the other measures 3 feet 2 inches round the octagonal end. The first gives 10½" diameter from one face to an opposite face, through the pillar, and the breadth of the square shaft of the largest section at the Lāt Masjid is 10½" at its upper end, while the breadth of the square part of the middle section is 10½". The width then of the smaller section is practically the same as the square part in the other two sections. But the perimeter of the octagonal end of the middle piece gives a diameter of 11½", which shows how unequal the diameter is in different parts. It seems quite clear, however, that the shortest piece does not immediately join on to the middle piece as there would be a sudden lessening from 11½" diameter to 10½", and I think we must conclude that there is a missing piece which fitted between these. The proportion of the octagonal part of the whole pillar to the square portion, as shown in the drawing, seems also to require greater length in the former. The total length of the original pillar was probably little short of 50 feet."

idea, and Mr. Lele, in his measurements, marks the positions of these. May not these really be silver imperfectly mixed with the iron, from silver mounted weapons. Tradition ascribes the column to Vikramāditya or Bhoja, but I would rather place it in the time of Arjunavarmadeva, say about A.D. 1210. It would have been a better finished piece of work from the hands of Rājā Bhoja.

HENRY COUSENS.